

Inequality in Access to Higher Education in Russia

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Abstract

Using data from the Trajectories in Education and Careers (TrEC) longitudinal panel study from 2011 to 2015, we empirically examine the effects of economic, geographic, and gender-based barriers on access to higher education in Russia. Our approach is designed to identify both direct and indirect impacts on the probability of university enrolment. Direct impacts are those that directly affect enrolment, while indirect impacts affect enrolment operating through aspirations to enrol in higher education. The direct impacts of income and place of residence on the probability of university enrolment, net of the effects of aspirations, are significant: a higher income increases the probability of university enrolment by between 5.3 and 18.8 percentage points depending on the income level, and living in a city increases the probability by between 6.0 and 10.9 percentage points compared to living in a rural area. In contrast, the net direct impact of gender on the probability of university enrolment is statistically non-significant; however, the indirect impact, operating through educational aspirations, is significant: girls are 4.4 percentage points more likely to intend to enrol in higher education. The net direct probability of university enrolment is independent of gender. Although a child's gender does not directly hinder university enrolment, it exerts a significant indirect influence by shaping girls' aspirations to enrol at university much more than it does for boys.

Keywords

access to higher education, inequality of opportunity, selective universities, socio-economic status, pupils' aspirations, TrEC, economic policy

JEL codes: I24, I25, I28, J24

Introduction

Human capital is becoming increasingly important in the modern world for economic and social development. Education is the primary source of human capital and the primary predictor of an individual's future income (Mincer 1958; Schultz 1961; Becker 1962). The litera-

ture also points to a link between education and better health (Lleras-Muney 2005), higher life satisfaction (Powdthavee et al. 2015) and reduced crime rate (Lochner 2020). Moreover, investment in education is valuable not only to individuals, but also generates positive externalities for society as a whole (McMahon 1987).

The literature distinguishes between factors influencing investment in education that depend on an individual's efforts or abilities, and those that are beyond their control, i.e. circumstances. Inequality of circumstances hinders the ability to make informed choices about education and is considered unfair (Ferreira and Gignoux 2014). Apart from the social aspect, equal opportunities in education are also important from an economic efficiency perspective. Inequality in access to education hinders the development of human skills, resulting in insufficient human capital and negatively impacting economic development (Chiu 1998; Mejía and St-Pierre 2008). Furthermore, social well-being deteriorates when people with higher abilities do not receive the education they merit (Willis and Rosen 1979; Willis 1986). Finally, in the long term, unequal educational opportunities caused and perpetuated by economic inequality may contribute to the so-called Great Gatsby Curve, a persistent association between high inequality and low intergenerational income mobility (Hassler et al. 2007; Corak 2013). In this scenario, education would no longer function as a factor of social mobility (Malinovskiy and Shibanova 2022a).

From an economic efficiency perspective, ensuring equal access to all levels of education is important. This paper focuses on inequality in access to higher education. Firstly, as V.E. Gimpelson noted, higher education in Russia provides individuals with a higher future income compared to other levels of education (Gimpelson 2019). Secondly, in recent years, higher education has become increasingly widespread in Russia (Education in Figures 2024), and enrolment immediately after high school is the main educational pathway (Soboleva 2023). Finally, although universities offer a number of state-funded places, higher education is a contested resource and tuition fees are rising in both absolute and relative terms (Rosstat 2023a; Monitoring the quality of enrollment in Russian universities 2022b). Access to higher education may depend on factors other than applicants' abilities, as evidenced by the displacement of low-income groups from the system (Malinovskiy and Shibanova 2022b). In a country as vast as Russia, geographic aspects of inequality in access to higher education, and to selective universities in particular, become even more pronounced. A high level of differentiation in educational quality and the geographic concentration of selective universities prevent regional universities from matching the higher quality of education offered by their competition located in large urban areas (Ministry of Science of Russia 2022; Rosstat 2023b; Monitoring the quality of enrollment in Russian universities 2022a).

On the one hand, circumstances beyond a pupil's control may directly affect their likelihood of continuing their education (Duru-Bellat et al. 2008; Ferreira and Gignoux 2010; Roshchina 2010; Ilieva-Trichkova and Boyadjieva 2014; Kosyakova et al. 2016; Bogdanov and Malik 2020). On the other hand, empirical literature shows that the same also predict pupil's aspirations regarding higher education (Appadurai 2004; Ray 2006; Dalton et al. 2016; Agger et al. 2018; Soboleva 2023). The question is whether the direct or indirect impacts of circumstances have a stronger influence on the probability of enrolling in higher education in Russia. This study takes an empirical approach to identifying the two channels through which circumstances influence the likelihood of enrolling in higher education and estimates this influence on enrolment net of the impact of circumstances on aspirations (and consequently enrolment). The study is based on data from a longitudinal survey of Russian pupils. This is the first study of its kind in the Russian context.

The paper is divided into five sections. The first section provides a systematic review of theoretical and empirical studies examining and assessing factors of inequality in access to higher education. The second section examines the data used; the third section presents the empirical strategy; the fourth section conducts econometric estimation; and the fifth section tests the robustness of the findings. The conclusion discusses the interpretation and the implications of the findings for economic policy.

Inequality in Access to Higher Education: A Review of the Literature

In the second half of the last century, the theory of equal opportunities transformed the perspectives of welfare theorists by arguing that policy assessment requires information about both the final welfare-related outcomes and the extent to which individuals are responsible for them (Bowles 1973; Conlisk 1974). Therefore, factors can be divided into 'efforts' and 'circumstances' (Roemer 1998). In this case, inequality of effort refers to characteristics that vary due to human effort and are under human control through free choice. Inequality of opportunity, on the other hand, is the difference in factors that are independent of the individual and prevent them from making conscious choices about the acquisition, consumption and disposal of resources. According to this theory, inequality can be divided into two types: 'fair' inequality, resulting from different levels of effort and ability leading to different achievements (inequality of achievement); and 'unfair' inequality, arising from circumstances beyond a person's control (inequality of opportunity) (Ferreira and Gignoux 2014).

Inequality of opportunity can manifest itself in various ways, including constraints on an individual's or group's ability to access benefits compared to another individual or group. Of particular importance is inequality of access to socially significant benefits, such as education, because consuming these benefits generates positive externalities. Inequality of access to education hinders the realisation of an individual's potential, which is the ability to transform resources into income-generating activities that depend directly on an individual's effort. This, in turn, reduces the accumulation of human capital, negatively impacting economic development (Chiu 1998; Mejía and St-Pierre 2008).

According to the model developed by S. Rosen and R. Willis, individuals consider their abilities and preferences, as well as their financing opportunities affecting the interest rate at which they can borrow against future income, in choosing the optimal level of investment in education (Willis and Rosen 1979; Willis 1986). Inequality of opportunity due to factors affecting financing opportunities and interest rates (a proxy for marginal costs) leads to losses in social well-being. This is particularly the case as more capable individuals with fewer opportunities do not receive an adequate level of education.

Higher education is a contested resource, and access to it provides pupils with an opportunity to enrol at university (Roshchina 2010; Ferreira and Gignoux 2010; Ilieva-Trichkova and Boyadjieva 2014; Khavenson and Chirkina 2019; Kersha 2021). This access is fair if it minimizes dependence on circumstances while maximizing dependence on the abilities and efforts of high school leavers (Roshina 2005; Roshchina 2010).

While there is a general agreement on the existence and definition of unequal access to higher education, there is still no consensus on how to measure it. Of the various methods described in the literature, one method stands out: measuring the extent to which the probability of university enrolment depends on factors beyond an individual's own efforts

(Roshchina 2010; Ferreira and Gignoux 2010; Ilieva-Trichkova and Boyadjieva 2014). The choice of educational trajectory (i.e. the sequence of academic statuses) is also considered, and this is usually not limited to a binary choice of whether to enrol (Duru-Bellat et al. 2008; Kosyakova et al. 2016; Bogdanov and Malik 2020). This approach enables to consider not only enrolment per se, but also the qualitative differences in opportunities available to different groups of pupils in terms of field of study, type of curriculum and type of university (Breen and Jonsson 2000; Lucas 2001; Ilieva-Trichkova and Boyadjieva 2014; Kosyakova et al. 2016).

A pupil’s future education and the decisions to be made about it depend on a variety of factors. First and foremost, pupils are guided by their academic achievements, which provide a benchmark for their abilities (Valentine et al. 2004). In addition, the socioeconomic status (SES) of the prospective university student’s family is considered. This is essentially a combination of the above-mentioned circumstances – factors that are beyond the individual’s control.

In the empirical literature, circumstances-related factors include about a dozen basic parameters: gender; family characteristics, such as parents’ level of education, which is an indicator of the family’s human capital, as well as a predictor of their income and their views on their child’s education; family composition; father’s occupation; family income; mother’s native language; family residence, including the region, the type of settlement, the distance to the nearest educational institution; migration status; number of books in the home; durable goods in the household; and school-related indicators, such as the location and type of school (gymnasium, lyceum, or regular high school) (Roshina 2005; Morgan 2012; Ferreira and Gignoux 2014; Prakhov 2014; Türk 2019).

Another area of research in this field involves identifying the mechanisms whereby these factors influence decision-making. According to (Boudon 1974), family characteristics, SES, and other circumstances influence a child’s academic achievement and preparation for enrolment (Figure 1, arrows 1a and 1b) as well as the shift to the next educational level (Figure 1, arrow 2). According to his theory, this influence is characterized by primary and secondary effects of SES.

As noted in (Erikson et al. 2005; Morgan 2012; Kosyakova et al. 2016; Khavenson and Chirkina 2019), primary effects indicate an indirect influence of factors independent of effort on the outcome through a child’s academic achievement. Pupils from families with

Figure 1. Primary and Secondary Effects of Social Background. *Source:* compiled by the author based on (Boudon 1974).

higher human, cultural, and economic capital tend to have higher educational achievements and, partly because of that, are more likely to continue their education. Secondary effects are expressed through the influence of other factors, such as parental expectations, resources, and values, on different educational trajectories among children with the same educational outcomes at the previous stage. This effect may result in children from families with a higher SES choosing more 'prestigious' trajectories more often, regardless of their academic achievement. In contrast, children from families with a lower SES may discontinue their education, even if their academic achievement is high. This conceptual framework can help distinguish the effects of pupils' choices from the influence of their immediate environment (Morgan 2012).

One way the family's socioeconomic status and other circumstances influence enrolment is through aspirations – differences in pupils' desires to enrol in higher education. Aspirations generally reflect one's desires for the future and various aspects of life and well-being. These desires determine one's choices, including goal setting, and the efforts one makes (Ray 2006; Durlauf et al. 2022). It is noted in (Morgan 2007; Khattab 2015) that aspirations include idealistic goals that imply the best possible outcomes.

In (Appadurai 2004; Ray 2006; Dalton et al. 2016), the authors demonstrate that societal influences shape aspirations, which explains why children from the least affluent groups believe they cannot achieve much, even though they may be more capable. The immediate environment, including parents, teachers, and peers, also influences aspirations by acting as role models or promoting social norms (Beaman et al. 2012; Macours and Vakis 2014; Baker et al. 2014; Heckman and Landersø 2022; Riley 2024; Soboleva 2023).

An important conclusion from this theory is that aspirations formed under the influence of circumstances influence outcomes. This has been demonstrated in studies based on data from various countries (Khattab 2015; Wu and Bai 2015; Agger et al. 2018; Fruttero et al. 2021).

Numerous studies on inequality of opportunity in Russian higher education highlight the importance of household income, place of residence, and the child's gender (Roshina 2005; Konstantinovskiy et al. 2006; Plokhova 2009; Roshchina 2010; Prakhov 2014; Kosyakova et al. 2016; Bessudnov and Malik 2016; Khavenson and Chirkina 2018; Khavenson and Chirkina 2019; Francesconi et al. 2019; Prakhov and Yudkevich 2019; Bogdanov and Malik 2020). In (Roshina 2005; Prakhov 2014; Kosyakova et al. 2016), the authors note the importance of the family's socioeconomic status through (1) the parents' ability to provide better preparation for their children through additional or initially higher levels of schooling (direct effect); and (2) a general aspiration among children from less well-off families (as well as from single-parent families) to opt for less 'prestigious' educational trajectories (indirect effect). (Soboleva 2023) presents empirical estimates confirming the impact of the family socio-economic status on the desire to continue education after Year 9, given equal academic abilities. The same author also notes that choosing a lower educational level to be achieved may be due to limited information available and/or a lack of motivation.

Despite the prevalence of studies on inequality in access to higher education in Russia, the empirical estimation of the impact of circumstances on the probability of university enrolment, considering both direct and indirect effects (the latter operating through the aspirations), remains an open issue. In the empirical literature, when controlling for abilities, the impact of factors independent of efforts on the outcome is estimated *separately* (Ferreira and Gignoux 2010; Ilieva-Trichkova and Boyadjieva 2014; Kosyakova et al. 2016; Bessudnov and Malik 2016; Khavenson and Chirkina 2019) (Figure 2, arrows 1a, 1b, 2) from the impact on aspirations (Garg et al. 2002; McCarron and Inkelas 2006; Soboleva 2023) (Fig-

ure 2, arrow 3a). The direct impact of SES (circumstances) on the outcome, net of its impact on aspirations (Figure 2, arrow 3b), remains unclear. This aspect is central to this study. Below, we propose an empirical approach to identifying the two channels through which circumstances influence enrolling in higher education, and to estimating the impact of circumstances on enrolment net of their impact on aspirations (and, consequently, enrolment).

Figure 2. Impact of circumstances on university enrolment. *Source:* compiled by the author.

Data and hypotheses

This empirical study used data from the national panel of the Russian Longitudinal Study of Trajectories in Education and Careers (TrEC)¹ and the international database on students, parents, teachers and schools TIMSS-2011². The study uses a cross-section of characteristics presented for different waves of the same respondents.

The sample was formed based on TIMSS-2011 Year 8-pupils in Russia; the same database supplied information about schools. The other characteristics mainly relate to Wave 1 and Wave 4 of TrEC. For the purposes of this study, the sample was limited to the common ‘Year 9 – Year 11 – university’ trajectory, chosen by over 60% of pupils (Soboleva 2023)³.

1 This paper used data from the panel study ‘Trajectories in Education and Careers’ (TrEC – <http://trec.hse.ru/>). The study was conducted with the support of the Fundamental Research Programme of the National Research University Higher School of Economics.

TrEC is the first longitudinal study of the educational and career choices of young people in Russia, conducted since 2011 after joining the international survey TIMSS. It involved 5,000 Russian schoolchildren who were in their Year 8 in 2011. Wave 1 took place in 2011–2012, when the participants were aged 15–16 and were in their Year 9. Wave 2 took place in 2013–2014, when the participants were aged 17–18 and were in their Year 11 or studied in further education colleges. Wave 3 took place in the Spring of 2014, and Wave 4 was conducted until the end of Autumn 2015, including first- and second-year students at universities or further education colleges.

2 TIMSS 2011 Assessment. Copyright © 2009 International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA). Publisher: TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education, Boston College. – URL: <https://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2011/international-database.html>

3 According to the same source, 29% of schoolchildren choose to continue their education in further education institutions after Year 9. The influence of SES on educational choices, such as whether to study in Year 11 or attend a further education college, is beyond the scope of this paper.

So, the study considered children who started their Year 11 in 2013, some of whom were enrolled in university by 2015. Table A1 in Appendix contains a list of all the variables and their sources. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for the used variables.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Variables Used

Variable	Number of observations	Average value	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value
University enrolment	2609	0.568	0.495	0	1
Selectivity of university	1190	0.350	0.477	0	1
Pupil's aspirations	2284	0.854	0.352	0	1
Family income	2422	2.022	1.101	1	5
Gender	2612	0.530	0.499	0	1
Mother's educational level	2595	3.584	1.299	1	6
Number of children in the family	2612	1.911	0.950	1	12
TIMSS mathematics scores	2612	545.335	74.908	319.66	804.03
Year 8 average academic achievement	2534	3.872	0.584	2	5
School type	2572	0.441	0.497	0	1
Type of settlement (a set of binary variables)					
City	2676	0.171	0.376	0	1
Suburb	2676	0.107	0.309	0	1
Medium-sized city	2676	0.462	0.499	0	1
Small town	2676	0.067	0.251	0	1
Remote rural areas	2676	0.170	0.376	0	1
Level of family wealth in school (a set of binary variables)					
Majority of disadvantaged families	2676	0.159	0.366	0	1
Majority of better-off families	2676	0.654	0.476	0	1
Neither group dominates	2676	0.187	0.390	0	1

Source: compiled by the author based on TrEC data.

Among the sample characteristics, the uneven distribution by type of settlement is notable, with almost half of the respondents living in medium-sized cities. Furthermore, 85% of respondents (Year 11 pupils or further education college students) intend to enrol in higher education. These factors should therefore be considered in further econometric estimation.

The correlation matrix of the variables under consideration, presented in Appendix (Figure A1), indicates that there is no significant multicollinearity between the charac-

teristics. It should be noted that two measures of ability are available in the data: TIMSS mathematics scores and average academic achievement in Year 8. These two indicators are correlated, with a correlation coefficient of 0.52. Nevertheless, both variables are included in the main model.

The data contains parents' assessments of the economic constraints affecting their children's access to higher education. In Wave 1, as the pupils were in their Year 9, parents were asked to suggest reasons why their children might not enrol in higher education (see Table 2). High tuition fees were cited by 59.42% of respondents, providing additional motivation to statistically test for the existence of these barriers while controlling for other determinants of enrolment probability.

Table 2. Distribution of parents' answers to the question 'What do you think are the main reasons which might prevent your child from enrolling in higher education after high school?'

Main reason for not enrolling in higher education	Number of observations	Proportion of sample
High tuition fee	1407	59.42%
Distance from universities	116	4.9%
Low scores	362	15.29%
Higher education is not required for the job	48	2.03%
They need to earn money	49	2.07%
They need to take care of a family member	11	0.46%
Illness, poor health	101	4.27%
Lack of motivation	70	2.96%
Other	204	8.61%
Total observations	2368	100%

Source: compiled by the author based on TrEC Wave 1 data.

Table 3 shows the distribution of circumstances (gender, family income, and type of settlement) for the whole sample and separately for those who did and did not enrol in university. It should be noted that the proportion of individuals who enrolled in university increases with income. Families with incomes of less than 20.000 roubles (42%) and between 20.000 and 29.000 roubles (27.7%) are most prevalent in the overall sample. The distribution by type of settlement shows that the proportion of those who enrolled is lower among rural residents compared with other types of settlement. It should also be noted that this proportion increases with the size of the city (small town – medium-sized city – large city). The sample is evenly divided between girls and boys, but on average, the proportion of enrolled girls is higher than that of boys.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the data has several limitations. Firstly, different parameters are presented for different time periods, which may distort some outcomes (for example, due to change of residence or school, variations in income or family composition between Year 8 and Year 11, etc.). Secondly, measurement errors due to self-assessment and missing values are present in the TrEC data collected through surveys.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the variable ‘Enrolment at university’ by family income, type of settlement, and gender

	Proportion of sample	Number of observations	including ‘Enrolment at university’ equals		Average value
			0	1	
Family Income					
below 20.000 roubles	42.0%	1017	587	430	0.423
20.000 to 29.000 roubles	27.7%	670	287	383	0.572
30.000 to 49.000 roubles	19.6%	473	139	334	0.706
50.000 to 79.000 roubles	7.3%	177	34	143	0.808
over 80.000 roubles	3.4%	82	16	66	0.805
Total	100%	2419	1063	1356	0.561
Type of settlement					
Remote rural areas	17.4%	454	283	171	0.377
City	17.5%	457	150	307	0.672
Suburb	10.9%	284	133	151	0.532
Medium-sized city	47.3%	1235	471	764	0.619
Small town	6.9%	179	90	89	0.497
Total	100%	2609	1127	1482	0.568
Gender					
male	0.47	1226	603	623	0.508
female	0.53	1383	524	859	0.621
Total	100%	2609	1127	1482	0.568

Source: compiled by the author based on TrEC Wave 1 and Wave 4 data and TIMSS-2011 data.

The following hypotheses are proposed based on the literature review and descriptive analysis of the data:

Hypothesis 1: Controlling for abilities, circumstances such as family income, place of residence and the child’s gender have a significant impact on the probability of enrolling at university.

- the higher the family income, the higher the probability of enrolment;
- pupils living in rural areas are less likely to enrol at university;
- boys are more likely to enrol at university.

Hypothesis 2: Controlling for abilities, circumstances such as family income, place of residence and the child’s gender have a statistically significant impact on the probability of enrolling in a selective university. The expected signs of the effect are similar to those in Hypothesis 1.

Hypothesis 3: Accounting for the impact of circumstances, such as family income, place of residence and the child’s gender, on the aspiration to enrol at university significantly reduces the impact of these circumstances on enrolment probability. The indirect impact of circumstances is statistically significant: children’s aspirations prevent them from realising their potential.

Empirical strategy

As noted earlier, a pupil's access to higher education is primarily the opportunity to enrol at university. In an empirical analysis, evidence of unequal access would be demonstrated by a statistically significant impact of factors independent of the pupil on the probability of university enrolment (Roshchina 2010; Ferreira and Gignoux 2010; Ilieva-Trichkova and Boyadjieva 2014; Bessudnov and Malik 2016; Khavenson and Chirkina 2019). Non-linear probit models were used to statistically estimate the determinants of the probability of enrolling at university.

To test Hypothesis 1, we performed probit regression analyses, using the probability of university enrolment as the dependent variable and circumstances, abilities and aspirations as the explanatory variables. Hypothesis 2 was tested using the probability of enrolment at a selective university as the dependent variable, with the same explanatory variables used to test the first hypothesis. Hypothesis 3 was tested using two models: a main model and an auxiliary model. In the auxiliary probit model, the dependent variable was the pupil's aspiration to enrol in higher education, while the explanatory variables included measures of circumstances and abilities. Based on the results of the auxiliary regression analysis, a variable representing unexplained residuals was constructed and included in the equation for the probability of university enrolment, replacing the original aspirations variable. This approach enables to control the direct impact of circumstances on university enrolment for their indirect impact (through their influence on intentions/aspirations). The auxiliary regression accounts for indirect impact. Including the residuals of this regression in the main equation retains the impact of aspirations in the model while interpreting the coefficients at the circumstances variables as direct impact, net of indirect impact. The estimated coefficient at residual (from the auxiliary regression) is interpreted as the impact of aspirations on the probability to enrol at university, net of (measured) circumstances and abilities/efforts.

The dependent variable representing university enrolment was constructed based on the 'Academic Status' question in Wave 4 of the longitudinal survey (April–November 2015, at the end of its first year), with a value of 0 assigned to the response 'not currently enrolled and never studied at university'⁴ and a value of 1, to 'not currently enrolled, previously studied at university (was/was not awarded a degree)', 'interruption of studies', 'currently enrolled at university (format unknown/in-person/not in-person)'.

The dependent variable characterizing the probability of enrolling at a selective university is based on the university indicated as the place of study in Wave 4. The variable is also binary, with 1 referring to a university with an average Unified State Examination score for students enrolled in state-funded places through competitive admission in 2014 higher than or equal to 70, and 0 referring to all other universities. This definition of a selective university is similar to the one used in (Prakhov 2014; Bogdanov and Malik 2020)⁵, and is based on the data in (Monitoring the quality of enrollment in Russian universities 2014).

4 For the purposes of further regression analysis, all trajectories except those involving enrolling in higher education immediately after completing Year 11 were combined into the same group. This is because the authors compare the 'Year 9 – Year 11-university enrolment' trajectory, which is the most popular in Russia, with all other trajectories together.

5 There is no consensus in the literature on how to define 'selectivity of a university', as confirmed by (Roshchin and Rudakov 2016; Emelina et al. 2022; Rozhkova et al. 2023). In conducting this study, the authors prioritised papers that employed a more formalised, quantitatively measurable definition of selectivity, based on the minimum average score achieved in the Unified State Examination required for students to be eligible to enrol in state-funded places.

The variable representing a pupil's aspiration to enrol in higher education is binary and is based on responses obtained during the early to mid-point of Year 11 (Wave 2, Autumn/Winter 2013-14). Data from this period was chosen over data from the end of Year 11 to 'control as much as possible for expectations based on Unified State Examination results' (Soboleva 2023: 45). Responses to the question about the highest level of education intended to be achieved were considered and grouped into two categories: 0 – any level below higher education (incomplete secondary education, complete secondary education, primary vocational education, further education); and 1 – higher education and above (bachelor's degree, specialist's degree, master's degree, higher education without specifying the degree, two or more university degrees, postgraduate studies, and degrees above the master's level).

A review of Russian literature helped identify the variables of interest and control (Plokhova 2009; Bessudnov and Malik 2016; Kosyakova et al. 2016; Khavenson and Chirkina 2018; Khavenson and Chirkina 2019; Prakhov and Sergienko 2020; Bogdanov and Malik 2020; Kersha 2021; Soboleva 2023). The former include three measures of circumstances: total family income; the type of settlement where the respective high school is located during the pupil's Year 8; and the pupil's gender. The control variables are the mother's educational level and the number of children in the family. To control for abilities, we used TIMSS mathematics scores measured on a scale from 1 to 1000 and the average academic achievement in Year 8. To control for school characteristics, we included the type of high school the pupil completed or last attended and the family wealth level of the respective high school during the pupil's Year 8. It should be noted that, while the mother's education and the number of children in the family are circumstances, they are not the focus of this paper.

Two specifications were used in each case. First, the probability of university enrolment (i.e. the probability of being enrolled at a selective university) was estimated based on the variables of interest and the basic controls. However, ability was not taken into account. The second specification included control for the child's abilities and high school characteristics. This was done to emphasise the importance of controlling for the child's abilities, information about which is often missing from the data. In this respect, TrEC has a significant advantage, as it provides several measures of abilities and enables the statistical analysis of inequalities in educational access.

Findings

University enrolment

Two probit models were constructed with different sets of control variables (basic and extended, controlling for academic achievement and school characteristics) to estimate the probability of university enrolment after Year 11. Table 4 presents the average marginal effects (hereafter referred to as marginal effects) obtained from the regressions.

The coefficients at the binary variables in the family income categories are significant at the 1% level in both the basic and extended models. This suggests that, when controlling for pupil's abilities, family income remains a significant factor, with higher income increasing the probability of enrolment.

Even when accounting for a child's abilities and their school's characteristics, it was found that income did have an impact on university enrolment (Model 2). On average, a pupil from a family with an income between 20.000 and 29.000 roubles was found to be 5.84 percentage points (p.p.) more likely to be enrolled compared with a family with an income

Table 4. Results of probit regressions estimating the probability of university enrolment (marginal effects)

Dependent variable: University enrolment		Model 1	Model 2
Variables		Basic	Control for academic achievement
Type of settlement. Relative to <i>Remote rural areas</i>	City	0.114*** (0.0346)	0.0788** (0.0331)
	Suburb	0.0199 (0.0375)	0.0465 (0.0339)
	Medium-sized city	0.0924*** (0.0280)	0.0809*** (0.0262)
	Small town	0.0588 (0.0418)	0.100*** (0.0349)
	20,000 to 29,000 roubles	0.0891*** (0.0238)	0.0584*** (0.0207)
Family income. Relative to <i>Below 20,000 roubles</i>	30,000 to 49,000 roubles	0.194*** (0.0265)	0.114*** (0.0247)
	50,000 to 79,000 roubles	0.271*** (0.0371)	0.161*** (0.0357)
	over 80,000 roubles	0.251*** (0.0542)	0.167*** (0.0511)
	female	0.127*** (0.0180)	0.0315* (0.0171)
Level of family wealth of school. Relative to <i>Majority of disadvantaged families</i>	Majority of better-off families		0.0357 (0.0248)
	Neither group dominates		0.0473 (0.0291)
	Mother’s educational level	0.0950*** (0.00682)	0.0414*** (0.00669)
Control variables	Number of children in the family	-0.0246** (0.0104)	-0.0268*** (0.00868)
	TIMSS mathematics scores		0.000776*** (0.000134)
	Average academic achievement in Year 8		0.282*** (0.0161)
	High school type		0.0877*** (0.0179)
Number of observations		2,408	2,303

Source: compiled by the author based on TrEC Wave 1 and Wave 4 data and TIMSS-2011 data. Note: robust standard errors are shown in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 correspond to the levels of significance 1%, 5%, and 10%. The results obtained are consistent with the findings of a study of inequality of opportunity based on different data for Russia. This highlights the family SES impact on access to education through various factors (Ibragimova and Frants 2021).

below 20,000 roubles. This figure was found to increase to 11.4 p.p. for incomes between 30,000 and 49,000 roubles, 16.1 p.p. for incomes between 50,000 and 79,000 roubles, and 16.7 p.p. for incomes over 80,000 roubles. Comparing the absolute values with the outcomes of Model 1 shows that including academic achievement and school characteristics in the model reduces the impact of a household's economic status. As previously mentioned, this can be explained by direct impacts, such as better preparation of children through access to additional resources and higher-quality schooling, the family being able to afford to relocate for their child's enrolment at university, and the family's ability to cover higher expenses during studies, including tuition fees. It can also be explained by an indirect impact operating through child's aspirations.

The positive coefficient estimates for all settlement type dummy variables in both specifications indicate an increased probability of university enrolment for children from all types of localities relative to rural areas. Large and medium-sized cities have a significant impact on access to higher education at 1% and 5% levels, respectively, which can be partly explained by the hypothesis of the concentration of educational institutions in large centres of population. For example, all other things being equal, a school leaver living in a large city is 7.88 percentage points (p.p.) more likely to enrol at university compared with a rural area; 8.09 p.p., a medium-sized city; and 10 p.p., a small town. However, no statistically significant impact was found for suburban areas.

Interestingly, gender inequality is present in both the basic and extended models. However, controlling for abilities greatly reduces its effect. Specifically, when controlling for abilities, the probability of a child enrolling at university is, on average, 3 percentage points higher for girls. This is significantly lower than the 12.7 percentage point difference observed in the first specification.

University selectivity

As previously mentioned, there is significant variation in the quality of education between Russian universities. For a researcher, the impact of the same factors on enrolment at universities of different quality is of particular interest. Selectivity is used as a proxy for this in the literature (Prakhov 2014; Bogdanov and Malik 2020). Table 5 presents the estimated probabilities of enrolment at a selective university.

The results show that the coefficients at the binary variables in the family income categories are significant at the 1% level in both models. This indicates that family income influences the probability of enrolling at a selective university, all other things being equal (including the pupil's abilities). In other words, a higher family income is associated with a higher probability of enrolling at a selective university, even more so than with university enrolment in general (Table 4, Model 2; and Table 5, Model 4).

Interestingly, place of residence ceases to be a statistically significant factor. This unexpected finding requires further study. This may suggest that selective universities have learned to select the most talented students based on their Unified State Examination (USE) scores, and that the USE admission mechanism has become more transparent. The findings suggest that enrolment at these universities is accessible regardless of the family's place of residence, all other things being equal.

The impact of a child's gender remains significant for enrolment at a selective university, with enrolment at a non-selective university serving as the basic category. All other things being equal, girls are, on average, 10.7 percentage points more likely to enrol at a selec-

Table 5. Results of probit regressions estimating the probability of enrolment at a selective university (marginal effects)

Dependent variable: University selectivity (≥ 70)		Model 3	Model 4
Variables		Basic	Control for academic achievement
Type of Settlement. Relative to <i>Remote rural areas</i>	City	0.113** (0.0560)	0.0643 (0.0591)
	Suburb	0.0504 (0.0622)	0.0440 (0.0644)
	Medium-sized city	0.0403 (0.0491)	0.0129 (0.0511)
	Small town	0.0297 (0.0707)	0.0540 (0.0730)
	20,000 to 29,000 roubles	0.0305 (0.0357)	0.0228 (0.0346)
Family income. Relative to <i>Below 20,000 roubles</i>	30,000 to 49,000 roubles	0.123*** (0.0390)	0.126*** (0.0386)
	50,000 to 79,000 roubles	0.132** (0.0531)	0.138*** (0.0522)
	over 80,000 roubles	0.244*** (0.0745)	0.251*** (0.0705)
	Gender	female	0.130*** (0.0288)
Level of family wealth in school. Relative to <i>Majority of disadvantaged families</i>	Majority of better-off families		0.109** (0.0444)
	Neither group dominates		0.0944* (0.0532)
	Mother’s educational level	0.0496*** (0.0121)	0.0345*** (0.0120)
	Number of children in the family	-0.00632 (0.0185)	-0.00305 (0.0172)
Control variables	TIMSS mathematics scores		0.000682*** (0.000262)
	Average academic achievement in Year 8		0.170*** (0.0318)
	High school type		0.0349 (0.0312)
	Number of observations	1,064	1,028

Source: compiled by the author based on TrEC Wave 1 and Wave 4 data, TIMSS-2011 data and (Monitoring the quality of enrollment in Russian universities 2014). Note: robust standard errors are shown in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 correspond to significance levels 1%, 5%, and 10%.

tive university than boys, which is higher than the corresponding estimated difference for university enrolment as a whole (3 percentage points). This finding can presumably be explained by girls' greater aspiration to enrol at a higher-quality university due to the gender pay gap.

Pupils' aspirations and estimate of direct impacts

As mentioned previously, to isolate the direct impact of circumstances on university enrolment and to control for the indirect impact operating through aspirations, an estimate was made of a model of aspirations to enrol in higher education (Model 5). Instead of the original aspiration variable (Model 6), regression residuals from Model 5 (aspirations) were included in the regression of the probability of enrolling at university. This retained control for aspirations while adjusting the aspirations variable for the impact of circumstances and thus obtaining an estimate of the direct impact of circumstances on university enrolment. The results are presented in Table 6. For ease of comparison, the results of Model 2 have also been added.

As anticipated, the coefficients at the direct impacts, adjusted for indirect impacts, declined in most cases, though the reductions were negligible and statistically non-significant in all cases except one. This suggests that the direct impact of circumstances on the probability of university enrolment is more significant than the indirect impact. However, it should be noted that circumstances with a small indirect impact are statistically significant in Model 5. This could suggest a kind of self-fulfilling prophecy, whereby intentions depend on circumstances to the extent that circumstances predetermine enrolment. More accurate testing of these mechanisms would necessitate a shift towards a broader model, a task that lies beyond the scope of this study.

The exception here is the child's gender: estimates suggest that the indirect impact of gender, operating through intentions, is significant, whereas the direct impact of gender on the probability of university enrolment is not. For example, in Model 6, differences in enrolment probability by gender are statistically non-significant, whereas gender significantly affects aspirations: girls are 4.4 percentage points more likely than boys to enrol in higher education. The absence of a gender impact in Model 6 (with all other factors, including intentions, held equal) suggests that there is no gender inequality in Russia's educational environment, especially with regard to university enrolment. The gender gap in favour of girls in the enrolment intentions model indicates high motivation among girls and low motivation among boys. The reasons for this disparity may be related to labour market or life expectancy factors, representing another interesting area for further research.

The direct impacts of income and place of residence on the probability of university enrolment are significant. On average, a pupil from a family with an income of 20.000 to 29.000 roubles is 5.27 percentage points more likely to enrol at university than a pupil from a family with an income of less than 20.000 roubles. The corresponding differences are 11.4 percentage points for incomes of 30.000 to 49.000 roubles, 18.8 percentage points for incomes of 50.000 to 79.000 roubles, and 14.9 percentage points for incomes of over 80.000 roubles. Among types of settlement, small towns and medium-sized cities are significant at the 1% level. Relative to children from remote rural areas, those from small towns and medium-sized cities are 10.9 percentage points and 6.4 percentage points more likely to enrol, correspondingly.

Table 6. Results of probit regressions estimating the probability of aspirations to enrol in higher education and actual university enrolment (marginal effects)

		Model 5	Model 6	Model 2
Variables		Aspirations (early Year 11)	Enrolment	Enrolment
Type of Settlement. Relative to <i>Remote rural areas</i>	City	0.0866*** (0.0254)	0.0602* (0.0342)	0.0788** (0.0331)
	Suburb	0.0443* (0.0269)	0.0269 (0.0355)	0.0465 (0.0339)
	Medium-sized city	0.0364 (0.0223)	0.0640** (0.0272)	0.0809*** (0.0262)
	Small town	-0.00100 (0.0322)	0.109*** (0.0366)	0.100*** (0.0349)
	20,000 to 29,000 roubles	0.00859 (0.0172)	0.0527** (0.0215)	0.0584*** (0.0207)
Family income. Relative to <i>Below 20,000 roubles</i>	30,000 to 49,000 roubles	0.0600*** (0.0194)	0.114*** (0.0256)	0.114*** (0.0247)
	50,000 to 79,000 roubles	0.0784*** (0.0278)	0.188*** (0.0358)	0.161*** (0.0357)
	over 80,000 roubles	-0.0347 (0.0492)	0.149*** (0.0547)	0.167*** (0.0511)
	female	0.0443*** (0.0142)	0.0249 (0.0176)	0.0315* (0.0171)
Regression residuals 5	Aspirations		0.221*** (0.0261)	
Level of family wealth of school. Relative to <i>Majority of disadvantaged families</i>	Majority of better-off families	0.0355* (0.0210)	0.0265 (0.0255)	0.0357 (0.0248)
	Neither group dominates	0.0749*** (0.0230)	0.0490 (0.0298)	0.0473 (0.0291)
	Mother’s educational level	0.0242*** (0.00587)	0.0394*** (0.00698)	0.0414*** (0.00669)
	Number of children in the family	0.00625 (0.00743)	-0.0246*** (0.00934)	-0.0268*** (0.00868)
Control variables	TIMSS mathematics scores	0.000329*** (0.000115)	0.000831*** (0.000138)	0.000776*** (0.000134)
	Average academic achievement in Year 8	0.170*** (0.0157)	0.271*** (0.0168)	0.282*** (0.0161)
	High school type	0.0525*** (0.0164)	0.0975*** (0.0183)	0.0877*** (0.0179)
	Number of observations	2,024	2,023	2,303

Source: compiled by the author based on TrEC Wave 1 and Wave 4 data, TIMSS-2011 data, and (Monitoring the quality of enrollment in Russian universities 2014). Note: robust standard errors are shown in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 correspond to significance levels 1%, 5%, and 10%.

Robustness check

To verify the robustness of the results, additional models were evaluated, including (1) alternative variables as proxies for the factors being tested, or (2) additional parameters not included in the previous models.

Economic factor. Family income, as reported by pupils' parents during TrEC Wave 1, was previously used as a proxy for household economic status. Later, in Wave 2 of the longitudinal study, the pupils themselves were asked about their perception of their family's financial situation. The correlation coefficient between this variable and income is 0.27, and the distribution of responses by income level is presented in Appendix (Table A2). Using an alternative measure of material status in the probit regressions did not lead to significant variation, confirming the robustness of the obtained estimates (see Appendix, Table A3).

Geographic factor. Previously, type of settlement was used as a proxy for the geographic location of households, the rationale being the territory's socio-economic status. However, population size is another characteristic of the area that can be analysed. The correlation coefficient between this variable and the type of settlement is 0.88; the distribution of responses by type of settlement is presented in Appendix (Table A4). The estimates of the new model specifications using the previous sets of variables are presented in Appendix (Table A5), which confirms the conclusion regarding the stable impact of the main factors on the probability of university enrolment.

Aspirations. In the empirical literature on the student aspirations theory, the main factors influencing their formation are not only the external, objective characteristics of the family or school, but also parental involvement in the learning process, educational expectations and the relationship between students and teachers, as well as other psychological parameters (Garg et al. 2002; Baker et al. 2014; Wu and Bai 2015; Agger et al. 2018). Table 6 in Appendix presents the estimation results of the probit regressions (Models 13 and 14), which use student aspirations to enrol in higher education as the dependent variable. In one case, the independent variables include a variable representing the educational level that parents want for their child, and in another case, the independent variables include a variable representing the educational level that parents expect their child to achieve. Based on the obtained estimates, we can conclude the following: First, parental educational expectations influence pupils' aspirations, with the expected level having a greater impact than the desired level. Second, family income significantly influences aspirations.

To verify the robustness of these results regarding the direct impacts of circumstances on the probability of university enrolment with a different specification of the equation of aspirations, estimations were made of the regressions with residuals from Models 13 and 14 (Models 15 and 16). The results confirm the robustness of the previously obtained estimates.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the empirical study conducted using Russian TrEC data, estimates were obtained of the direct impact of circumstances (family income, place of residence, and child's gender) on the probability of university enrolment. This direct impact was then adjusted for the indirect impact, i.e. the influence of these circumstances on pupils' aspirations to enrol in higher education. The estimates suggest inequality of access, as well as the

presence of economic barriers (household income is a statistically significant factor) and geographic barriers (place of residence is a statistically significant factor).

The direct, adjusted impacts of income and place of residence on the probability of enrolling at university are significant. Depending on the income level, a higher income increases this probability by between 5.3 and 18.8 percentage points. Meanwhile, living in a city increases this probability by between 6.0 and 10.9 percentage points compared to living in a rural area. Interestingly, the adjusted impacts of economic and geographic barriers to accessing higher education are statistically similar to the unadjusted impacts, i.e. the impacts obtained without including these barriers in the empirical model. Perhaps a self-fulfilling prophecy is at work here, whereby intentions reflect existing economic and geographic barriers to accessing higher education.

In this context, the finding regarding the impact of a child's gender (circumstance) on access to higher education is particularly interesting, with the indirect impact of gender, operating through intentions, proving significant, while the direct adjusted impact of gender on the probability of university enrolment being statistically non-significant. While a child's gender does not directly prevent them from enrolling at university, it has a significant indirect impact, shaping girls' intentions to enrol to a much greater extent than boys'. The factors behind this gender gap in intentions and the roles of labour market institutions and the extremely high and persistent gender gap in life expectancy are interesting areas for further research.

Interestingly, place of residence has no significant impact on the probability of enrolling at a selective university (all other factors, including abilities, being equal), even though geography is a statistically significant determinant of university enrolment. This suggests that the transparency of the admission mechanism based on the Unified State Examination scores plays a positive role in levelling this aspect of inequality in access to higher education.

The analysis of the role of economic and geographic barriers to accessing higher education in Russia highlights the need to refine economic policy measures that would reduce existing barriers. Although there is international experience of using grants and educational loans to support the most talented students, Russia has yet to make full use of this approach (Herbaut and Geven 2019). Improving the quality of schools in rural areas, developing regional universities further, and promoting educational mobility through a student loan system can reduce the effect of geographic barriers (Malinovskiy and Shibanova 2022a; Roshina 2005). The gender gap in university enrolment intentions remains unaddressed, particularly regarding the relatively low motivation among boys. This could result in long-term losses in social well-being.

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Appendix

Table A1. List of variables used and their descriptions

Name of Variable	Type of Variable	Units of measurement, scale	Source
University enrolment	Dummy	0 – if the individual is not currently enrolled and never studied at university, 1 – if the individual is currently enrolled or studied at university.	TrEC Wave 4 (eQ_as_vo_2)
Gender	Dummy	0 – male, 1 – female.	TrEC Wave 1 (aQ1)
Mother's educational level	Categorical	1 – basic general education (9 years) or lower, 2 – secondary general education (10–11 years), 3 – primary/secondary vocational education, 4 – incomplete higher education, 5 – higher education, 6 – academic degree / two HE degrees.	TrEC Wave 1 (aS3_a) и TIMSS-2011 (BSBG06A)
Number of children in the family	Quantitative		TrEC Wave 1 (aS2)
TIMSS mathematics scores (Year 8)	Quantitative	Score (1-1000), where: 400-474: Low, 475-549: Intermediate, 550-624: High, 625-1000: Advanced.	TIMSS-2011 (BSMMAT01 – 05)
Average academic achievement in Year 8	Quantitative	Score (1-5)	TrEC Wave 1 (aQ11_1 - *8)
High school type	Dummy	0 – regular high school, 1 – any non-regular school (gymnasium, lyceum, a school that provides in-depth or specialised teaching of certain subjects, evening classes/adult secondary school).	TrEC Wave 4 (eQ3)
Type of Settlement (location of school)	Categorical	0 – remote rural areas, 1 – city, 2 – suburb, 3 – medium-sized city, 4 – small town.	TIMSS-2011 (BCBG05B)
Family income	Categorical	1 – below 20.000 roubles, 2 – 20.000 to 29.000 roubles, 3 – 30.000 to 49.000 roubles, 4 – 50.000 to 79.000 roubles, 5 – over 80.000 roubles.	TrEC Wave 1 (aS7)

Name of Variable	Type of Variable	Units of measurement, scale	Source
Level of family wealth of school	Categorical	1 – low-income, over 26%; most affluent, less than 25% / low-income families, over 50%, 2 – most affluent, over 26%; low-income, below 25% / most affluent, over 50%, 3 – all other combinations.	TIMSS-2011 (BCBG03A-B)
Selectivity of university	Dummy	0 – if the average USE score among those admitted through competitive selection in 2014 is below 70, 1 – if the average USE score among those admitted through competitive selection in 2014 is equal or above 70.	(Monitoring the quality of enrollment in Russian universities 2014)
Aspirations	Dummy	Highest intended level of education (as of start/middle of Year 11): 0 – other, 1 – HE and above (bachelor’s degree, specialist’s degree, master’s degree, two or more HE degrees, post-graduation school and academic degree).	TrEC Wave 2 (bQ45)
Family’s financial situation (pupil)	Categorical	0 – unable to afford even food / can afford food, unable to afford clothes and shoes / can afford clothes and shoes, unable to afford large household appliances, 1 – can afford large household appliances, unable to afford a new car, 2 – can afford anything except expensive purchases, such as an apartment or a house, 3 – no financial difficulties, could purchase an apartment or a house, if need be.	TrEC Wave 2 (bQ83)
Population size at school’s location	Categorical	0 – ≤ 3.000, 1 – > 500.000, 2 – 100.001 – 500.000, 3 – 50.001 – 100.000, 4 – 15.001 – 50.000, 5 – 3.001 – 15.000.	TIMSS-2011 (BCBG05A)
Desired educational level (parents)	Dummy	0 – other, 1 – HE or above (HE, two HE degrees or an academic degree).	TrEC Wave 1 (aS17)
Realistic expected educational level (parents)	Dummy	0 – other, 1 – HE or above (HE, two HE degrees or an academic degree).	TrEC Wave 1 (aS18)

Table A2. Distribution of family’s financial characteristics by income category

Family income	Family’s financial situation (pupil’s response)				Total observations
	Unable to afford large domestic appliances	Unable to afford a new car	Unable to afford expensive purchases, such as an apartment or a house	No financial difficulties, could afford an apartment or a house	
below 20.000 roubles	232 (28%)	232 (28%)	293 (35%)	70 (9%)	827 (100%)
20.000 to 29.000 roubles	88 (15.5%)	167 (29%)	225 (40%)	88 (15.5%)	568 (100%)
30.000 to 49.000 roubles	36 (9%)	111 (27%)	179 (43%)	85 (21%)	411 (100%)
50.000 to 79.000 roubles	8 (5%)	35 (23%)	64 (42%)	46 (30%)	153 (100%)
over 80.000 roubles	6 (10%)	8 (13%)	19 (30%)	29 (47%)	62 (100%)
Total observations	370 (18%)	553 (27%)	780 (39%)	318 (16%)	2.021 (100%)

Table A3. Results of probit regressions estimating the probability of enrolment, with material status as a proxy for the economic factor (marginal effects)

Dependent variable: University enrolment		Model 7	Model 8	Model 9
Variables		Basic	Control for academic achievement	Control for aspirations
Control variables	Gender	0.109*** (0.0194)	0.0221 (0.0181)	0.0230 (0.0187)
	Mother’s educational level	0.109*** (0.00698)	0.0445*** (0.00702)	0.0436*** (0.00727)
	Number of children in family	-0.0137 (0.0111)	-0.0183* (0.00951)	-0.0201** (0.00996)
	TIMSS mathematics scores		0.000916*** (0.000145)	0.000962*** (0.000148)
	Average academic achievement in Year 8		0.273*** (0.0171)	0.269*** (0.0177)
	High school type		0.112*** (0.0188)	0.112*** (0.0193)

Dependent variable: University enrolment		Model 7	Model 8	Model 9
Variables		Basic	Control for academic achievement	Control for aspirations
Regression residuals 5	Aspirations			0.227*** (0.0292)
Level of family wealth in school.	Majority of better-off families		0.0352 (0.0261)	0.0352 (0.0270)
Relative to <i>Majority of disadvantaged families</i>	Neither group dominates		0.0505 (0.0311)	0.0602* (0.0321)
	City	0.162*** (0.0357)	0.0985*** (0.0337)	0.0968*** (0.0356)
Type of Settlement.	Suburb	0.0584 (0.0417)	0.0536 (0.0366)	0.0334 (0.0382)
Relative to <i>Remote rural areas</i>	Medium-sized city	0.126*** (0.0302)	0.0850*** (0.0283)	0.0803*** (0.0294)
	Small town	0.0950** (0.0467)	0.108*** (0.0380)	0.125*** (0.0399)
	Unable to afford a new car	0.0820*** (0.0305)	0.0459* (0.0273)	0.0543* (0.0284)
Family's financial situation.	Unable to afford expensive purchases, such as an apartment or a house	0.0764*** (0.0287)	0.0709*** (0.0258)	0.0792*** (0.0269)
Relative to <i>Unable to afford large domestic appliances</i>	No financial difficulties, could afford an apartment or a house	0.0848** (0.0348)	0.0833*** (0.0306)	0.0883*** (0.0320)
	Number of observations	2.155	2.064	1.838

Note: Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 correspond to significance levels 1%, 5%, and 10%.

Table A4. Distribution of population size by type of settlement

Type of Settlement	Population size						Total observations
	> 500.000	100.001 – 500.000	50.001 – 100.000	15.001 – 50.000	3.001 – 15.000	≤ 3.000	
City	440 (96%)	17 (4%)	–	–	–	–	457 (100%)
Suburb	285 (100%)	–	–	–	–	–	285 (100%)
Medium-sized city or a large settlement	16 (1%)	540 (44%)	207 (17%)	421 (34%)	51 (4%)	–	1.235 (100%)
Small town or urban village	–	–	–	40 (22%)	132 (73%)	8 (4%)	180 (100%)
Remote rural areas	–	–	–	21 (5%)	200 (44%)	234 (51%)	455 (100%)
Total observations	741 (28%)	557 (21%)	207 (8%)	482 (19%)	383 (15%)	242 (9%)	2.612 (100%)

Table A5. Results of probit regressions estimating the probability of enrolment, with population size as a proxy for the geographic factor (marginal effects)

Dependent variable: University enrolment		Model 10	Model 11	Model 12
	Variables	Basic	Control for academic achievement	Control for aspirations
Control variables	Gender	0.128*** (0.0179)	0.0351** (0.0170)	0.0275 (0.0176)
	Mother’s educational level	0.0926*** (0.00682)	0.0397*** (0.00665)	0.0377*** (0.00697)
	Number of children in the family	-0.0237** (0.0102)	-0.0279*** (0.00863)	-0.0251*** (0.00929)
	TIMSS mathematics scores		0.000852*** (0.000135)	0.000903*** (0.000140)
	Average academic achievement in Year 8		0.277*** (0.0162)	0.266*** (0.0170)
	High school type		0.0841*** (0.0179)	0.0940*** (0.0184)
	Regression residuals 5	Aspirations		

Dependent variable: University enrolment		Model 10	Model 11	Model 12
Variables		Basic	Control for academic achievement	Control for aspirations
Level of family wealth in school. Relative to <i>Majority of disadvantaged families</i>	Majority of better-off families		0.0120 (0.0252)	0.00366 (0.0254)
	Neither group dominates		0.0150 (0.0294)	0.0174 (0.0300)
	> 500,000	0.166*** (0.0386)	0.140*** (0.0368)	0.124*** (0.0391)
	100.001 – 500.000	0.146*** (0.0397)	0.131*** (0.0372)	0.124*** (0.0394)
Population size. Relative to $\leq 3,000$	50.001 – 100.000	0.174*** (0.0459)	0.135*** (0.0421)	0.116** (0.0450)
	15.001 – 50.000	0.235*** (0.0395)	0.219*** (0.0373)	0.193*** (0.0392)
	3.001 – 15.000	0.140*** (0.0400)	0.132*** (0.0376)	0.139*** (0.0398)
	20.000 to 29.000 roubles	0.0894*** (0.0237)	0.0585*** (0.0207)	0.0544** (0.0215)
Family income. Relative to <i>Below 20,000 roubles</i>	30.000 to 49.000 roubles	0.192*** (0.0263)	0.109*** (0.0244)	0.111*** (0.0254)
	50.000 to 79.000 roubles	0.274*** (0.0369)	0.166*** (0.0357)	0.194*** (0.0352)
	over 80.000 roubles	0.261*** (0.0524)	0.177*** (0.0497)	0.156*** (0.0523)
	Number of observations	2.408	2.303	2.023

Note: Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 correspond to significance levels 1%, 5%, and 10%.

Table A6. Results of probit regressions estimating the probability of aspirations to enrol in higher education and of actually enrolling at university, net of parents’ educational expectations (marginal effects).

		Model 13	Model 14	Model 15	Model 16	
Variables		Aspirations	Aspirations	Enrolment	Enrolment	
Control variables	Gender	0.0377*** (0.0140)	0.0385*** (0.0138)	0.0248 (0.0178)	0.0261 (0.0178)	
	Mother’s educational level	0.0166*** (0.00591)	0.0144** (0.00583)	0.0406*** (0.00703)	0.0397*** (0.00704)	
	Number of children in family	0.00675 (0.00712)	0.00523 (0.00687)	-0.0232** (0.00939)	-0.0235** (0.00942)	
	TIMSS mathematics scores	0.000289** (0.000113)	0.000290*** (0.000110)	0.000827*** (0.000140)	0.000845*** (0.000140)	
	Average academic achievement in Year 8	0.141*** (0.0160)	0.114*** (0.0160)	0.272*** (0.0170)	0.271*** (0.0170)	
	High school type	0.0477*** (0.0162)	0.0401** (0.0161)	0.0954*** (0.0185)	0.0943*** (0.0185)	
	Desired educational level (parents)	0.0862*** (0.0148)				
	Realistic expected educational level (parents)		0.116*** (0.0144)			
	Regression residuals 13	Aspirations, while accounting for the desired level			0.202*** (0.0265)	
	Regression residuals 14	Aspirations, while accounting for the expected level				0.189*** (0.0270)
Level of family wealth in school.	Majority of better-off families	0.0318 (0.0201)	0.0375* (0.0200)	0.0259 (0.0256)	0.0264 (0.0258)	
	Relative to Majority of disadvantaged families	0.0717*** (0.0222)	0.0744*** (0.0223)	0.0491 (0.0301)	0.0472 (0.0303)	
Type of Settlement.	City	0.0751*** (0.0252)	0.0702*** (0.0251)	0.0591* (0.0343)	0.0546 (0.0344)	
	Suburb	0.0398 (0.0263)	0.0375 (0.0255)	0.0267 (0.0355)	0.0238 (0.0356)	
	Relative to Remote rural areas	0.0315 (0.0217)	0.0296 (0.0212)	0.0627** (0.0272)	0.0594** (0.0272)	
	Small town	-4.58e-05 (0.0315)	-0.00398 (0.0311)	0.108*** (0.0370)	0.107*** (0.0370)	

		Model 13	Model 14	Model 15	Model 16
Variables		Aspirations	Aspirations	Enrolment	Enrolment
Family income. Relative to <i>Below</i> 20,000 roubles	20.000	-0.00281	0.00358	0.0548**	0.0553**
	to 29.000 roubles	(0.0171)	(0.0167)	(0.0217)	(0.0217)
	30.000	0.0512***	0.0531***	0.116***	0.120***
	to 49.000 roubles	(0.0193)	(0.0194)	(0.0259)	(0.0260)
	50.000	0.0783***	0.0748***	0.189***	0.191***
	to 79.000 roubles	(0.0258)	(0.0267)	(0.0363)	(0.0364)
	over 80.000 roubles	-0.0498 (0.0493)	-0.0630 (0.0496)	0.146*** (0.0556)	0.144*** (0.0554)
Number of observations	2.002	1.995	2.001	1.994	

Note: Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$ correspond to significance levels 1%, 5%, and 10%.